

UAP Operational Presence 1945-1975 - Details on Individual Incidents

Military Reports During 1947 to 1951 Involving Multiple Incidents During a Day, From the Sparks catalog

March 6 to March 8, 1952

March 6, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 8:20 [9?] p.m. Army artillery observers with triangulation equipment, Sgt. Hubert Vickery and PFC John Ransom, on patrol at the AFSWP (Armed Forces Special Weapons Project) national nuclear weapons storage Site B saw a blue-white oblong object about 2 ft x 1 ft in size with a trail travel from 286° to 279° azimuth elevation 5°45' [6°45'? 6°41'? poss. typos] height about 600 ft. No sound. Other sightings by Army patrols from 8:30 p.m. [8:45? 9?], 1:10, 1:15 to 2 a.m. (Sparks 172; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 412, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 6, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 8:45 p.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw a light-colored round object with trail about 10° long travel S to N from azimuth 189° elevation 21° to azimuth 210° elevation 6°31'. No sound. Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 173; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 6, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 9 [8:20?] p.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw a blue-white ball-like "fixed flash," size of basketball [?], in the NE at azimuth 40° elevation 59°. No sound or trail. Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 174; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 1:15 a.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw a brilliant blue-white flash of light like flashbulb in the NE at azimuth 40° elevation 66°15'. No sound. [Meteor?] Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 175; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 1:30 a.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw a blue-white ball-like "fixed flash," size of basketball [?], in the NNE at azimuth 16° elevation 27°30'. No sound. [Meteor?] Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 176; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 1:30-2 a.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw a bluish-white ball-like flash of light like flashbulb in the WSW at azimuth 250° elevation 26°. No sound. Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 177; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 1:45 a.m. Army artillery observation patrol saw an orange tear-drop shaped object, 2 x 1 ft in size [?], drop vertically to ground, in the ENE at azimuth 60°. No sound. [Meteor?]

Other sightings by Army patrols (see above, below). (Sparks 178; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 413, Maxwell Roll 5, p. 627; FOIA)

March 7, 1949. Window Rock, Ariz. 6:10 p.m. Sighting of round object fire red in the center shading to blue at edge, 3 ft in diameter [?], traveling estimated 200-300 mph, in the N at elevation 40°-45° disintegrating at the end. No sound. (Sparks 179; BB NARA Microfilm Roll 91, p. 414)

March 8, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 1:03 [2?] a.m. Army artillery observation patrols in separate locations 1/2 mile apart sight different [?] lights, one pale white light with roundish head and hazy smoke trail (streak? 900 ft height?) seen by Payne moving in an arc from 122° to 126° azimuth [southward?] from 58° to 54° elevation, the other, by Cpl. Luke Sims, was of a lemon-shaped red light with whitish nose and red trail in level flight about 15° above horizon crossing 60° of sky from 304° to 244° azimuth [WNW to WSW]. (Sparks 180; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 5, p. 627, Roll 91, p. 414; FOIA; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

March 8, 1949. Los Alamos and Kirtland AFB, New Mexico. 6:35-6:36 p.m. Los Alamos AESS guards Patterson and Lang at guard stations 103 and 106 saw noiseless greenish-white light in the WSW heading SE, descending at 60° [45°] angle. Kirtland Control Tower saw same object to the NW descending vertically. (Sparks 181; BB Microfilm Roll 88, p. 373, Roll 91, p. 414; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

May 5 to May 9, 1952

May 5, 1949. Ft. Bliss, Texas. 11:40 a.m. Army officers Maj. Day [May?], Maj. Olhausen, Capt. Vaughn saw 2 oblong white discs, flying at about 200-250 mph, make a shallow turn. (Sparks 214; Berliner)

May 6, 1949. Sidney, Ohio. 8:30 a.m. Stump, Herman and Quinn saw a bright object about 1/2 mile to the W moving S at high speed, no trail or sound, one saying it was too bright to see the shape the other saying it had a flat circular shape. (Sparks 215; FOIA; Saunders/FUFOR Index; Jan Aldrich)

May 6, 1949. Livermore, Calif. (37.69° N, 121.76° W). 9:35 a.m. C. G. Green saw 2 shiny, disc-like objects rotate around each other and bank, then one shot upwards with a grey trail and rejoined the other. (Sparks 216; Berliner)

May 6, 1949. Los Alamos, New Mexico. 1:05 a.m. N to S 5° above horizon was going down at an angle of 30° - 35° green none round very high rate of speed disappeared west of Jemez Mts (1) (Sparks 217; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

May 6, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 8:40-9:30 p.m. (CST). UFO observation network using Army artillery observers, headed by Task Force Commander Lt. Mardell E. Ward, established 2 days earlier after a series of unexplained UFO incidents over the previous 2 months observed by 100+ men and officers, tracks its first object with artillery sighting instruments, field binoculars and Battery Commander 25-40x scope. Brilliant light to the W and N, moving back and forth 900 to 1,200 ft (around?) azimuth 292.5° [WNW], tracked by all 4 Observation Posts at distance 12,000 ft [from main Plotting Center], height 1200 ft dropping to 440 ft, alternating pinkish to green, apparent size 1/2 dollar at arm's length diminishing to quarter coin size, moving very slow, faded from sight by growing smaller [with

distance]. Project Grudge claimed UFO was Venus, ignoring the multiple 2-mile triangulations, and the fact Venus set at about 7:37 p.m. CST. (Sparks 218; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 5, p. 628, Roll 91, pp. 414ff.; FOIA; Jan Aldrich)

May 7, 1949. S St. Louis, Missouri (38.63° N, 90.21° W). 7 p.m. (CST). Just after sunset Vaughn saw the sun glinting off a flat reddish-brown object, "somewhat triangular" shaped, oscillating, the size of a private plane but faster. (Sparks 219; FOIA; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

May 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 7:40 p.m. (CST). Lt. Mardell E. Ward, at the Plotting Center (command post) of the Army's UFO observation and triangulation network established May 4, and an artillery observer at another network observation site, spotted a brilliant white (reddish greenish white?) diamond-shaped object at triangulated location 15,000 ft away at 1,000 ft height to the N and the E headed NW. Object was tracked for 57 seconds as it traveled horizontally 20 mils arc [not miles; about 1.1°] about 300 ft at about 3½ mph while changing color from white to reddish to greenish as it dropped altitude and dimmed then disappeared. Object size measured at about 45 ft, from angular size 3 mils (about 0.17° at 15,000 ft range). Battery Commander scope used, 25x-40x. No sound. [Another sighting 8:25-9:05 p.m.] (Sparks 220; FOIA; Jan Aldrich; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; Loren Gross Jan-Jun 1949 Supp p. 79, erroneously put at Los Alamos; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 5, p. 628)

May 7, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 8:25-9:05 p.m. Lt. Mardell E. Ward, at the Plotting Center (command post) of the Army's UFO observation and triangulation network, and artillery observers at 3 other network observation sites, spotted a brilliant (green-white?) white diamond-shaped object in the SE (and W) at triangulated location 24,000 ft away at 1,300 ft height. Object size measured at about 72 ft (angular width 3 mils or about 0.17°), was tracked for 40 mins as it traveled 15 mils arc [not miles; about 0.8°] about 360 ft at about 0.1 mph. Battery Commander scope used, 25x-40x. No sound. (Sparks 221; FOIA; Jan Aldrich; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; Loren Gross Jan-Jun 1949 Supp p. 79, erroneously put at Los Alamos; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 5, p. 628)

May 8, 1949. Killeen Base/Site B [Nuclear Weapons National Stockpile], Camp Hood, Texas (31° 3'53" N, 97°49'40" W). 8:08-8:17 p.m. Lt. Mardell E. Ward, at the Army's UFO observation post, and 2 other posts sighted brilliant (reddish greenish white?) diamond-shaped object to the W (and N and E) moving NW or NE at about 24,000 ft distance at 1,600 ft height slowly dropping. Object size measured at about 48 ft (angular width 2 mils or about 0.1°), was tracked for 9 mins as it traveled 10 mils arc [not miles; about 0.5°] about 240 ft at 0.3 mph. Severe radio interference during sighting, none afterward. (Sparks 222; FOIA; Jan Aldrich; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; Loren Gross Jan-Jun 1949 Supp p. 80, erroneously put at Los Alamos; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 5, p. 628)

May 8, 1949. Tucson, Ariz. (32.23° N, 110.96° W). 9:30 - 11 a.m. MSgt. Troy Putn a.m. [?] plus 3 other witnesses saw round, flat silvery object, about 40-75 ft diameter, in the W flying faster than a jet, in horizontal flight at 4,000 ft, make 90° turn to the N, then rapid climb at 45° angle until out of sight. (Sparks 223; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

May 9, 1949. Tucson, Ariz. (32.23° N, 110.96° W). About 2:30 p.m. MSgt. Troy Putn a.m. saw two round, flat silvery objects, about 25 ft diameter, flying 750-1,000 mph in a banking but steady manner, from SW to NE, which faded from view. (Sparks 224; Saunders/FUFOR Index; Randle)

May 9, 1949. White Sands Proving Ground. WSPG Naval Unit Commander, Cdr. Robert L. McLaughlin, with several other officers, witnessed UFO near a WAC-B rocket just launched. (Sparks 225; McLaughlin ltr to Van Allen, May 12, 1949)

August 6, 1949

Aug. 6, 1949. Las Cruces, Alamogordo, New Mexico. 8:00 p.m. Alamogordo: 200° 30° above horizon long slow curve to earth bluish green Yes 1 sec none round tip of thumb at arm's length burned out (1) Las Cruces: E to W bluish green Yes 1-2 secs none round bigger than falling star disappeared behind building (1) (Sparks 262; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

Aug. 6, 1949. Las Cruces, White Sands, Alamogordo, New Mexico. 8:00 p.m. Las Cruces: E to W 3° 28" to 9° 40" above horizon curve going up then fell in almost vertical direction reddish blue & green Yes 4-5 secs none round app 6" in diameter disappeared gradually (1) White Sands: 40° above horizon straight line to earth observer color blind none 1 sec none round half size of fingernail at arm's length slightly faster than ordinary falling star disappeared behind sand dune (1) (Sparks 263; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

Aug. 6, 1949. Alamogordo, New Mexico. Bet. 8:00-8:05 p.m. E to W 2° 4" to 12° 7" above horizon 10° off vertical [upwards] white 2 secs none large as auto spotlight at arm's length disappeared behind building (1) vertical 2° 20" to 7° 35" above horizon straight vertical flight [upwards] bright white slight reddish cast none 3 secs none round 1/2 size of moon exploded then pieces died out (1) (Sparks 264; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.) BB UNKs Catalog version 1.30 / Jan. 26, 2020 / © 2020 Brad Sparks -70-

Aug. 6, 1949. Albuquerque, New Mexico. 8:20 p.m. descending to earth vertically 15° above horizon green none round to pear shape 500-watt bulb about 1/5 mile [?] away 10° in 1 1/2 secs at 2 miles [?] dissipated (1) (Sparks 265; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

Aug. 6, 1949. Alamogordo, New Mexico. 8:30 p.m. N constant slight curve earthward white (bluish) Yes none round app smaller than clenched fist similar to falling star went out (1) (Sparks 266; AFOSI-LaPaz Catalog May 1950; BB Microfilm Roll 91, pp. 414ff.)

Selected Reports During 1952 From Sparks List

From the Sparks catalog

May 1, 1952 (for military incidents, there are no civilian cases in Sparks for May 1, 1952)

May 1, 1952. Moses Lake, Wash. (47.13° N, 119.29° W). 5:32 a.m. (PST). AEC employees Eggan and Shipley saw a silver object without wings fly straight and level. (Sparks 566; Berliner)

May 1, 1952. Davis-Monthan AFB, Tucson, Ariz. 9:10 a.m. (MST). Base Intelligence Officer Major Rudolph Pestalozzi, M/Sgt. Edmund L. Bouton, Jr., and several others saw 2 shiny round 20-28-foot objects rapidly overtake then pace a B-36 in E-W flight at 20,000 ft at about 50° ±10° elevation, then depart at high speed, one object stopping to hover briefly, before disappearing, no sound, no trail. B-36 crew also saw objects and interrogated on landing. (Sparks; Case file was not missing; McDonald did not have a date or even the precise year.) (Maxwell BB Microfilm Roll 10, pp. 332-341; Hynek UFO Rpt pp. 109-112; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

May 1, 1952. George AFB and Apple Valley, Calif. 10:50 a.m. (PDT?). 3 men on the arms range, plus Lt. Col. Lyle Albert Silvernail 4 miles away in Apple Valley saw 5 flat white discs about the diameter of a C-47's wingspan [95 ft] or length of P-51 [32 ft] fly fast about 1,000 mph at about 4,000 ft height, make a 90° turn in a formation of 3 in front and 2 behind, and dart around. Silvernail reported the sighting and was told radar was tracking the object(s) and fighters were being scrambled. (Sparks; Berliner; NICAP)

June 23, 1952 (for military incidents, civilian cases also included)

June 23, 1952. Spokane, Wash. 4:05 p.m. Airport weather observer Rex Thompson saw a round disc with a metallic shine flash, and flutter like a flipped coin. (Sparks 633; Berliner)

June 23, 1952. McChord AFB, Wash. 9 p.m. 2nd Lt. K. Thompson saw a very large light fly straight and level. No further information. (Sparks 634; Berliner)

June 23, 1952. Kirksville AFS, Missouri Kirksville, Missouri (at 40°17'52"N, 92°34'34"W). 1:30 and 1:35 a.m. (CST). USAF ADC 790th AC&W Sq FPS-10 radar (=CPS-6B minus early-warning search beam) radar operators Lt. A. N. Robinson, Jr., and Airman Ray H. Foote, plus 5 other controllers, officers and maintenance technicians, tracked single unidentified targets with a clear sharp return about the size of a B-29's (or B-50 or B-36). First target suddenly appeared at 88 NM (101 stat. miles) at azimuth 357° (almost due N) of radar site, and continued outward from the radar site on an approximately straight line with blips appearing on 15-second sweeps of the rotating radar be a.m. at 88, 100, 114, 132, 146, 158, 174, 180, and 205 NM from radar site (intervals in jumps of 12, 14, 18, 14, 12, 16, 6, and 15 NM), thus moving at a highly variable speed of about 1,650 to 5,000 mph, or about an overall average of 4,000 mph. Second target suddenly appeared at 1:35 a.m. at 94 NM (108 stat. miles) again at azimuth 357° (almost due N) of radar site, and continued outward from the radar site on an approximately straight line with blips appearing on 15-second sweeps of the rotating radar be a.m. at 94, 109, 124, 141, 154, 168, and 187 NM from radar site (intervals in jumps of 15, 15, 17, 13, 14, 19 NM), thus moving at a variable speed of about 3,600 to 5,200 mph, or about an overall average of 4,300 mph. Possible radar interference with radial outward highspeed tracks on identical azimuths not crossing to other side of scope. But identity of interfering radar is unknown, the failure of tracks to extend into center of scope and to the outer edge (contrary to erroneous initial teletype report claiming

the latter) is unexplained, failure to appear for 3 minutes between tracks (1:32 to 1:35 a.m.) is unexplained, and great variability of apparent speed (contrary to one erroneous report) is also unexplained. No other ADC radar site reported interference, which should have been mutual and equal, and none again from the 357° azimuth despite new incidents at all compass directions on July 12, 1952. Missing BB case file was in Hynek's files at CUFOS. (Sparks 635; Hynek-CUFOS files)

June 23, 1952. Oak Ridge, Tenn. 3:30 a.m. Secretary Martha Milligan saw a bullet-shaped object with burnt orange exhaust fly straight and level. (Sparks 636; Berliner)

June 23, 1952. Location unknown, but information came via Japan Hq "CV 4359." 6:08 a.m. USAF pilot Wermack of the 18th Fighter-Bomber Group saw a black coin-shaped object, 15-20 ft in diameter, at 6,000 ft approach to within 1,500 ft, then make an irregular descent. (Sparks 637; Berliner; Project 1947)

June 23, 1952. Near Owensboro, Kentucky. 10 a.m. National Guard Lt. Col. O. L. Depp heard sound, saw 2 objects looking like "giant soap bubbles" reflecting yellow and lavender colors, fly in trail. (Sparks 638; Berliner; Randle)

Description of Reports from Sparks List During July 22 to July 29, 1952 (military and public)

July 22, 1952

July 22, 1952. Los Alamos, New Mexico. 10:50 [11:05] a.m. Control tower operator Don R. Wiens and 2 CARCO pilots, Jack E. Chinn and F. Dew, and fireman I. V. Rowland, saw 8-10 large, round or bell-shaped, bright aluminum objects fly straight and level, then dart around erratically. First overhead then headed SW where one object disappeared into or behind a cumulus cloud about 10-15 miles away over James Mtns. (Sparks; Berliner; BB Maxwell Microfilm Roll 12, pp. 1012-6, etc., Misc Roll 1, pp. 506-8) (Sparks 701)

July 22, 1952. July 22 [?], 1952. Stafford, Virginia. 12 p.m. USAF pilot of C-54 transport saw a bright ovoid object hover then move in stops and starts, first approaching the plane then paralleling it. (Sparks; Berliner; Loren Gross) (Sparks 702)

July 22, 1952. Brookley. AFB, Mobile, Alabama (BBU). 2 p.m. USAF Tech Sgt. and a civilian employee saw a barrel-shaped black object 3.5-4 ft diameter, emitting black smoke trail and a black puff of smoke flying about 5,000 ft above ground 1 mile away heading Ethen flying "perpendicular" (vertical?). 2 mins. (Hynek-CUFOS-Willy Smith files) (sparks 703)

July. 22, 1952. July 22, 1952. Uvalde, Texas. 2:46 p.m. Don Epperly, Trans Texas Airlines station manager and weather observer, saw a large, round, silver object fly at 1,000+ mph while gyrating. (Sparks; Berliner) (sparks 704)

July. 22, 1952. 12 miles E of Peterson Field, Colo. (BBU) 6:45 p.m. USAF ADC personnel in Cessna 140 and the pilot saw a round silver object disappear into clouds. (Project 1947) (sparks 705)

July. 22, 1952; Near Braintree, bet. Boston and Provincetown, Mass. (BBU 1556) 10:20 and 10:47 p.m. (EST). USAF pilot and radar operator of F-94B jet interceptor saw a large round spinning object throwing off a blue light. At 10:47 p.m., same or different F-94B jet fighter chased bluegreen or green object circling at high speed, with airborne radar tracking and lock on. Another[?] F-94 intercepted 2

objects with flickering white light and swishing circling blue light which passed the jet, with airborne radar tracking and ground visual observation. [Confusion with Misawa case below??] (Berliner; cf. Weinstein) (sparks 706)

July 22, 1952. Near Braintree, bet. Boston and Provincetown, Mass. (at 42°10' N, 71°01' W) [?]. 10:20-10:30 p.m. (EST). 3 F-94 crews at 15,000 ft, all 5 men aboard saw a large round spinning white flickering object at estimated 26,000 ft throwing off a swishing circling blue light or considered to be 2 objects. One F-94 climbed to 35,000 ft at 250 knots with afterburner obtained radar contact for about 1 min at 10:47 p.m. Lt. Emil Lemieux and radar operator Lt Richard A. Schaffer of F-94B jet interceptor at 10:20 p.m., at 42°10' N, 71° W, heading 90° at 200 knots at 20,000 ft sighted object at same height or slightly higher on the left heading 270°, which passed at about 1 mile distance. F-94 made 180° turn to pursue and kicked in afterburner, but UFO also made 180° turn and passed immediately above F-94 when it was seen to be a large white spinning object throwing off a blue light. F-94 went into extremely loose Lufbery ("Luftberry") defensive air combat maneuver, but UFO was above and flying faster and climbed and turned out of sight (at 38,000 ft?) at 10:30 p.m. Lt Schaffer unable to detect object on APG-33 radar. U.S. Weather Bureau Observer Guy M. Bailey at Balloon Observation Tower, Logan Airport, Boston, tracked object at estimated 7-10+ miles distance by theodolite from 10:15 to 10:26 p.m. (EST) remaining at relatively constant elevation 22° and moving 22° arc from azimuth 118° to 140° at about 25,000 ft climbing to 35,000 ft, changing color from bluish-white to red when decelerating then back to bluish-white when extremely rapidly accelerating, making 3 separate 360° elliptical circling movements near pibal balloon at about 200 mph between 20.0° to 20.5° and 23.0° elevation and between 118° and 130° azimuth. Not visible with naked eye, first seen while tracking weather balloon using theodolite telescope, and had to abandon UFO to continue weather duties. Single object consisted of 4 small red and green rounded-rectangular lights at times completely enveloped by single bluish-white light brighter than +1 magnitude star. [See previous cases above, next case below, and July 23 case.] (Sparks; BB & AFOSI files; Berliner; cf. Weinstein) (sparks 707)

July 22, 1952. Quincy, Mass (BBU 1556)

From 10:45 to 10:48 p.m. (EST) Officer of the Day, Navy Lt Cdr W. J. Adams, with Marine Air Detachment S/Sgt Anthony Di Nallo, at Squantum Naval Air Station, Quincy (and Navy Seaman Rolf Hellum 1 mile to Sand possibly 1-2 other base personnel) received calls from 6 civilians in area (total duration 7-8 mins apparently beginning about 10:40 p.m.) then looked and saw 2 blue-green lights brighter than magnitude + 1 stars maneuvering and passing over base, possibly at 800-900 mph at 40,000 to 50,000 ft, first seen in SE at 45° elevation then moved directly overhead [90°] reversed course back to SE to 45° elevation without noticeable turning, then again passed overhead this making wide arc to NE without changing altitude. Not dimmed by distance, disappeared suddenly as if switched turned off one light then the other at 10:48 p.m. (EST). (sparks 708)

July 22, 1952. MacDill AFB, Florida (BBU) 10:30 p.m. (EST). MacDill AFB air traffic control tower operator sighted for ½ hour a red-greenish-blue object to the WSW at about 45° elevation with 2 other [similar?] objects to the N of it, smaller and/or farther away and lower in elevation angle (?). Tower operator sighted another object to the SSE about 30° elevation at 11 :30 p.m. MacDill AFB Detachment 21, 3944th Radar Bomb-scoring Sq (RBS), radar tracked object at 12:03 a.m. (July 23) at azimuth 160° range 65,000 yards (37 mi) at 41,200 ft altitude on a heading of 310° True [almost directly towards MacDill AFB] speed 462 knots [532 mph]. Tampa Radar Bomb-scoring Sq also tracked object at 160° azimuth [about SSE] altitude 41 ,000 ft [reportedly, in 1998 account, Navy and CAA radars also tracked object]. At 12:08 a.m. USAF pilot and copilot of B-29 bomber with 364th Bomb Sq on landing approach were vectored by MacDill tower operator to investigate, saw high speed object at 40,000 ft heading towards MacDill AFB on a heading of 308° traveling faster than the B-29. 4

airmen at MacDill AFB radar site sighted object as it passed close [nearly overhead?]. (According to 1998 report of B-29 pilot, an AF Lt Col, they were flying at 20,000 ft; the B-29 fire control radar locked on to object at 40,000 ft and prepared to fire when UFO changed course and disappeared at 4,000 knots speed.) MacDill RBS lost object on radar at range 145,000 yards [82 mi] azimuth 310° (about NW) [at about 12:15 a.m.]. Civilians near base sighted object(s) visually. (Sparks; Robert Klinn; Project 1947; McDonald list; BB files; NICAP; NUFORC) (sparks 709)

July 22-23, 1952. Trenton, New Jersey. 10:50 p.m. - 12:45, 1:28-3:47 a.m. Crews of several USAF F-94 jet interceptors from Dover AFB, Del., made 13 visual sightings and one radar tracking of blue-white [orange?] lights. White, green and blue lights were seen by ground observers and F-94 pilots moving in arcs and blinking out suddenly. F-94 crew got radar lock-on at 30,000 ft away of object the size of an F-94, at 9,000 ft away the object made a sharp right turn, suddenly dropped in height and disappeared. Other sightings in the Dover-Trenton area. (Sparks 710; Berliner; Loren Gross)

July 23, 1952

July 23, 1952. Near Boston, Mass. 1:15-1:18 a.m. (EST). Watch duty CG Seaman Henry Arnpriester, Nahant Coast Guard Station, sighted 2 bluish flat disc-shaped objects side-by-side estimated 5 ft in diameter (at 1,100 to 2,000 ft altitude?) in the SE at about 45° elevation descending and headed NW towards him until reaching distance of about 1-1/2 miles when suddenly reversed direction like “a ball bouncing off a wall” returning to SE and climbing without any change in apparent speed until gradually disappearing due to distance. [See July 22 sightings near Boston / Braintree, Mass.] (Sparks 711; AFOSI files; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

July 23, 1952. Jamestown, Rhode Island. 7:36 a.m. USN radar tracked high speed target heading N at 42,000 ft and confirmed by ADC radar at Camp Hero, N.Y. F-94's and F-86's scrambled unsuccessfully. (Sparks 712; McDonald list; Loren Gross)

July 23, 1952. E of Misawa AFB, Japan. 8:20 p.m. USAF pilot flying F-94 jet fighter chased blue-green fireball. (Sparks 713; Weinstein)

July 23, 1952. Pottstown, Penna. 8:40 a.m. 2-man crews of 3 USAF F-94 jet on training mission saw a large silver object 50-300 ft in size, shaped like a long pear with 2-3 squares beneath it, flying at 150-180 knots (170-210 mph) headed W, while a smaller object, delta-shaped or swept back, flew around it at 1,000-1,500 knots (1,150-1,700 mph) for 1-4 mins. Possible Skyhook balloon with highspeed UFO. (Sparks 714; BB Maxwell files, roll 12, pp. 1173-1175; Berliner)

July 23, 1952. Altoona, Penna. 12:50 p.m. 2-man crews of 2 USAF F-94 jet interceptors at 35,000-46,000 ft altitude saw 3 cylindrical objects in a vertical stack formation fly at an altitude of 50,000-80,000 ft. (Sparks 715; Berliner)

July 23, 1952. South Bend, Indiana. 11:35 p.m. USAF pilot Capt. H. W. Kloth saw 2 bright blue-white objects flying together, then the rear one veered off. (Sparks 716; Berliner)

July 24, 1952

July 24, 1952. Carson Sink, Nevada. 3:40 p.m. (MST). USAF HQ Directorate of Operations Lt. Cols. John L. McGinn (Deputy of Ops, Fighter Br) and John R. Barton (AFOOP-OP-D) flying E in a B-25 bomber at 11,000 ft and 185 knots airspeed saw 3 silver white, delta-shaped or arrowhead-shaped

objects at their 1 o'clock position slightly larger than the size of F-86's (40 ft), each with a ridge along the top, in V-formation, cross in front of and above the B-25 from right to left (S to N) at about 1,200 to 2,400 ft away at about 1,800+ mph. (Sparks 717; Berliner; NARCAP; cf. Ruppelt pp. 10-1; NICAP)

July 24, 1952. Travis AFB, Calif. (Sparks 718; NARA)

July 25, 1952

July 25, 1952. Elmendorf AFB, Alaska. (Sparks 719; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

July 25, 1952. Wilmington, Delaware. Afternoon. VA employee saw 2 discs reflecting light in a climb. (Sparks 720)

July 26, 1952

July 26, 1952. Hampton, and bet. Newport News and Langley AFB, Virginia. 12:15-12:45? a.m. Ground observers saw a brilliant luminous alternately bright silver, red and green object hovering over the James River Bridge at about 1,500 ft for 1/2 hour, then ascend towards the E were seen by Langley AFB tower. USAF crews of 2 F- 94's and ground observers saw 4 round silver/bluish objects in V-formation shoot straight up and disappear at 5,000 ft, one tracked by USN ground radar at Norfolk and by airborne radars. (Sparks 721; Weinstein; Project 1947? Condon project?)

July 26, 1952. Kansas City, Missouri. 12:15 a.m. USAF Capt. H. A. Stone, men in control towers at Fairfax Field and Municipal Airport, saw a greenish light with red orange flashes descend in the NW from 40° to 10° elevation. (Sparks 722; Berliner)

July 26, 1952. Kirtland AFB, New Mexico. 12:05 a.m. Airman 1st Class J. M. Donaldson saw 8-10 orange balls in triangular or V-formation flying fast. (Sparks 723; Berliner)

July 26, 1952. Langley AFB, Virginia. 2:30 p.m. USAF Capt Daniel G. Moore, military air traffic controller with 1909-7 AACS Detachment, and Tech Sgt. Edward N. Rosner [Roaner?], tracked on MPN-1C radar an unidentified object from about 15 miles [probably NM] S to disappearance 8 miles [probably NM] S of site, speed about 2,600 mph [7 mi in 0.2 min is 2,100 knots or 2,400 mph], below 5,000 ft altitude, headed towards the air base. Duration of 2 mins in report must be typo for 0.2 min. No visual. Possible radar interference (high-speed target moving radially inward towards radar not crossing center of scope). See similar case below. (Sparks 724; Berliner; Randle; NICAP)

July 26, 1952. Langley AFB, Virginia. 2:50 p.m. Capt Daniel G. Moore, military air traffic controller with 1909- 7 AACS Detachment, and Gilfillan electronics technician Willi a.m. Yhope [Thorpe?] tracked a radar target moving E away from radar site at an unstated initial distance [possibly 8 NM if like case above], stopping for 2 mins [probably 0.2 min] at 12 miles [probably NM] E, again moving extremely fast, speed not estimated, disappearing at 15 miles [probably NM] E. Possible radar interference (high-speed target moving radially outward away from radar not having crossed center of scope). See similar case above. (Sparks 725; Berliner; NICAP)

July 26, 1952. Williams, Calif. 5:15 p.m. (PST). Case file missing. (Sparks; Randle) [N Calif. F-94C intercept case involving large orange-yellow object moving fast and slow, tracked by airborne and ground radars?? (Sparks 726; Weinstein)]

July 26, 1952. Plainview, Texas. 7:17 p.m. USAF pilot and copilot of T-33 saw a stationary object move in a slight descent changing color from white to blue. (Sparks 727; Project 1947)

July 26, 1952. Atlantic 200 miles S of New York City, New York. 8:30 p.m. USAF B-29 gunner, 301st Bomb Wing, saw 3 amber edged [?] white flashing objects traveling at Mach 1. (Sparks 728; Project 1947)

July 26, 1952. Florence, South Carolina. 10:04 [10:10?] p.m. Eastern Airlines Flight 606 Constellation pilot and 2 crew members saw a steady white light traveling at high speed in a straight line at 22,000 ft. (Sparks 729; Project 1947)

July 26-27, 1952. Andrews AFB and Washington National Airport, Wash., D.C. 8 p.m. [9:50? p.m. EDT] until after 12 midnight [1:00? a.m. EDT]. Radar operators at several airports, airline and F-94 fighter pilots, sighted and tracked many unidentified blips and/or lights all over Washington area, at varying speeds. (Sparks 730; Berliner)

July 27, 1952

July 27, 1952. Wilmington, Delaware. 7 p.m. (EDT)?). James R. Thomas saw a cylindrical object with domed top and bottom moving NW to SE in an upright position, disappearing suddenly. (Sparks 731; NARA; NICAP)

July 27, 1952. 10 miles SSW of Columbus, Ohio. 12:05 a.m. USAF pilot of B-25 with 3 Pentagon Colonels on board saw a white light with 4 flashing lights stationary then move. (Sparks 732; Project 1947)

July 27, 1952. Selfridge AFB, Mich. 10:05 a.m. 3 B-29 bomber crewmen on ground saw many round, white objects fly straight and level, very fast. Two at 10:05, one each at 10:10, 10:15, 10:20. [Possible Exercise SIGNPOST SAC B-36's from Carswell AFB enroute to simulated attack run on Detroit, Mich.??] (Sparks 733; Berliner)

July 27, 1952. Wichita Falls, Texas. 8:30 p.m. Mr. and Mrs. Adrian Ellis saw 2 disc-shaped objects, illuminated by a phosphorus light, fly at an estimated 1,000 mph. [Possible returning B-36's of Exercise SIGNPOST??] (Sparks 734; Berliner)

July 27, 1952. Manhattan Beach, Calif. (Sparks 735; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

July 28, 1952

July 28, 1952. McChord AFB, Wash. 2:15 a.m. T/Sgt. Walstead and S/Sgt. Calkins of the 635th AC&W Sq ADC radar site saw a dull, glowing, blue-green ball, size of a dime at arms' length, fly very fast, straight and level. (Sparks 736; Berliner)

July 28, 1952. Hallock, Minn. (Sparks 737; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

July 28, 1952. McGuire AFB, New Jersey. 6 a.m. GCA radar operator M/Sgt. W. F. Dees, and persons in the base control tower. Radar tracked a large cluster of very distinct blips. Visual observation was of

oblong objects having neither wings nor tail, which made a very fast turn, at one time in echelon formation. (Sparks 738; Berliner)

July 28, 1952. Heidelberg, West Germany (49°25' N, 8°42' E). 10:20 p.m. Sgt. B. C. Grassmoen and WAC PFC A.P. Turner saw a saucer-shaped object having appearance of light metal giving off shafts of white light, flying slow, make 90° turn and climb away fast. (Sparks 739; Berliner)

July 29, 1952

July 29 [28?], 1952. 20 miles W of Port Huron, Mich (at 43.0° N, 82.8° W). 9:40-10 p.m. (EST). One of 3 USAF F-94B's on an ECM exercise at 9,000-9,500 ft from 61st FIS at Selfridge AFB climbed to 20,000 ft on a 270° heading when it was vectored to a UFO headed S [or SE?] at 625 mph from Saginaw Bay by GCI air defense radar [apparently FPS-3, Port Austin AFS, Mich.] (callsign "Avenger") [tracked about 7 mins evidently]. Ground radar told pilot Capt. Edward J. Slowinski (Sloan) to look at his 3 o'clock low position for a target (to the N), but found nothing, then told to look at 3 o'clock high (radar man recalled "low" then "high," pilot said he was told "high" then "low"). F-94 turned right to pursue [~9:47 p.m.]. Object suddenly reversed course with a tight 180° turn back N on ground radar scope [evidently at 300 mph to match F-94's speed, in a visible loop on the radar scope on a right turn paralleling the F-94's right turn but tighter]. As the F-94 continued right turn, radar observer Lt. Victor Helfenbein picked up target at 4 miles range on APG-33 airborne radar, level with jet altitude, at 60° relative or 2 o'clock (about 330° to 360° azimuth depending on how far into the turn) (pilot said Helfenbein reported 2:30 o'clock). Airborne radar contact made [for possibly 20 secs during the turn] then at dead ahead 12 o'clock position radar got lock-on for 30 secs until target "jumped lock" when it apparently almost doubled its 4-mile [or 4-5 mi] distance in one sweep of the ground radar accelerating to 1,400 mph average speed [4-mile jump in 10-sec sweep of radar, thus reaching peak 2,600 mph at about 20 g's]. Jet briefly put on afterburner to try to close distance with object on 360° heading at 21,000 ft increasing speed with afterburner to about 350 knots IAS (about 490 knots TAS or 560 mph) [for about 3 mins?], but object would put on a burst of speed and pull away from the jet. F-94 pilot first saw multiple lights ahead as if from a jet aircraft, but no exhaust or trail, and followed the GCI vectoring to target ahead between 12 o'clock and 1 o'clock positions. Object appeared "many times larger than a star" then "took on a reddish tinge, and slowly began to get smaller, as if it were moving away," and changed color from reddish then bluish-green then white then red again in sequence (both crew members in agreement) low on the horizon to the N (possibly the star Capella and unrelated to radar target, though Helfenbein was an expert celestial navigator since 1943 with 1,400 flying hours and had never seen anything "like this before"; also another F-94 followed same N route about 10:30 p.m. with Capella still visible but did not see it as unusual or anything else). F-94 continued N heading [for about 5 mins] at about 300 mph as object maintained lead at 6-10 miles range, with GCI telling F-94 crew they were not gaining on the target on scope. Chase ended with F-94 about 5 miles N of peninsula (map shows 10 mi ENE of Burnt Cabin Point at 44°07' N, 82°45' W) return due to low fuel, object then slowed to 200-300 mph before disappearing after another 1-2 mins. (Sparks 740; McDonald 1968 & papers; Mary Castner / CUFOS; Loren Gross July 21-31, 1952 Supp pp. 71-77; Ruppelt pp. 171-172, 190; BB Status Rpt 8, pp. 27-28, in NARA Roll 85, pp.701-2, Maxwell Roll 1, pp. 674-5; Todd Lemire)

July 29, 1952. Osceola, Wisc. 1:30 a.m. Radar operators on ground and pilot of F-51 Mustang in flight. Several clusters of up to 10 small radar targets and one large target. Small targets moved from SW to E at 50-60 knots (60-70 mph), following each other. Large target moved at 600 knots (700 mph). Pilot confirmed one target. (Sparks 741; Berliner)

July 29, 1952. Walker AFB, Roswell, New Mexico. 4 weather observers including base weather officer sighted several high-speed discs through theodolite. (Sparks 742; Hynek UFO Rpt. pp. 114-5)

July 29, 1952. Los Alamos, New Mexico. 9:49 a.m. (MST). Several Los Alamos Scientific Lab employees, AESS guards and pilots on ground saw white or metallic object moving E to W to the N of the Los Alamos landing field, about 1.8°/sec [18°/min ?] angular velocity, with gyrating or fluttering motion. 2 F-86 jet interceptors from Kirtland AFB already in air were diverted and arrived about 3 mins later at 40,000 ft, object was in front of F-86's but was not seen by pilots, the UFO disappeared then reappeared having made 360° turn trailing behind fighters for 2 mins, then disappeared again. See sighting soon afterward (below). (Sparks 743; Hynek UFO Rpt pp. 61-64; BB Misc Microfilm Roll 1, pp. 506-8; BB Status Report 8, Dec 1952, p. 29; etc.)

July 29, 1952. Los Alamos, New Mexico. 9:57 [10:57?] a.m. (MST). Several Los Alamos Scientific Lab employees, AESS guards and pilots on ground [?] saw light-brown or white egg-shaped object with wings hovering then shot off to the NW disappearing in 3 secs. (Sparks 744; Hynek UFO Rpt pp. 61-64; BB Misc Microfilm Roll 1, pp. 506-8; BB Status Report 8, Dec 1952, p. 29; etc.)

July 29, 1952. Wichita, Kansas. 12:35 p.m. USAF shop employees Douglas and Hess at Municipal Airport saw a bright white circular object with a flat bottom fly very fast then hover 10-15 secs over the Cessna Aircraft Co. plant. (Sparks 745; Berliner)

July 29, 1952. 8 mi S of Ennis, Montana (at 45°14' N, 111°40.7' W, elev. 5300 ft). Between 2 and 3 p.m. [12:30?] (MST). US Army (res.) Maj. Ben Shaffer with wife and 3 children sighted and filmed objects with Bell & Howell color movie camera and Kodak Retina b&w still camera, and sighted with 8x binoculars, for 30+ mins between 3 and 4 p.m. (MST). Shaffer saw an object hovering about 1,000 ft over a mountain or hills [to the E] about 3-4 [7 ?] miles away, reportedly at 45°13' N, 111°32' W [Cedar Mtn, elev. 10,718 ft], while driving N, stopped the car, and stopped two other cars, for a total of about 12 witnesses, one of whom used 50x binoculars. The object formed a cloud around itself, then three smaller disc-like objects possibly jet fighter-sized (50 ft) burst out of the cloud from different angles at about 200 mph, forming an arc then disappeared. Another 5 small objects appeared on the right side of the cloud in V formation traveling slowly, then each of the small objects formed clouds around themselves, then re-entered the large cloud one behind the other. No other clouds in the sky. Near end of Shaffer's sighting another cloud suddenly appeared to the left of highway about 6 [13 ?] miles away [to the W] over Hill 9572 (9572 ft elev.) [Baldy Mtn?] at 45°11' N, 111°57' W, with same phenomenon of objects emerging and re-entering the cloud. ADC 29th Air Div, AACS (1906-5 Sq Detachment) and CAA checked for radar tracks, none reported. (Sparks 748; Martin Shough; NICAP; Berliner)

July 29, 1952. Great Falls AFB, Montana (47°30' N, 111°13' W). 3:25-4:48 p.m. (MST). 17+ military and civilian USAF personnel (possibly totaling 50) at AACS Sq, and 1701st Air Traffic Sq and 1701st Air Transport Wing and Wing Intelligence, Great Falls AFB were alerted by a Plan 62/Plan 113 inter-base intercom alert at 3:20 p.m. MST from McChord AFB, Seattle, Wash., of a possible incoming UFO, including USAF Maj. John J. LeGrand, Maj. Raymond L. Kolman, Capt. Roy J. Jackson, S/Sgt Donald M. Manchester, Lt Hilton D. Logan, Capt. Orin G. Harman, Lt John Macgill, Mrs Anne L. Macgill (off base 8 mi from Great Falls alerted by husband Lt Macgill), Miss Virginia Walbon, Airman Charles Hooks, Mrs Anne E. Mihalik, Mrs Margaret Evans (Western Union at GFAFB), Mrs Forrester, Airman Willi a.m. Cole, Airman Harold Bennett, S/Sgt Charles C. Boden, Jr., M/Sgt Clarence R. Stotesbury, T/Sgt Fernandez. McChord AFB transmission was cut off in mid-sentence right after the words "flying saucer" and base personnel later falsely denied ever making the alert (though heard by

multiple GFAFB personnel). Some GFAFB personnel had sightings possibly as early as 2:30 p.m. Disc-shaped object. ADC 29th Air Div, AACS (1906-5 Sq Detachment) and CAA checked for radar tracks, none reported. (Sparks 748; NICAP; Berliner)

July 29, 1952. Merced, Calif. 3:44 or 4:35 p.m. Herbert Mitchell and employee saw a dark, disc-shaped object, trailed by a silvery light 2 lengths behind, tipped on its side, dive, hesitate then circle very fast. (Sparks 748; Berliner; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

July 29, 1952. Albuquerque, NM. 10:30 p.m. (MST). Los Alamos Lab AEC employee pilot USAF Reserve Lt Col Robert G. LeCompte sighted from home a yellow luminous fattened ellipse 4° in length at 225° azimuth (SW) at 20° - 25° elevation, which began rapidly shrinking in size and changing color to yellowish-white then white after 45-60 secs while in the same motionless position, disappeared after another 15 secs. LeCompte noted setting half-moon [52% illumination] set at 10:57 p.m. MST [at azimuth 246°]. No sound. (Sparks 749; BB files; BB Status Report 8, Dec 1952, p. 30)

July 29 [not 30], 1952. Kirtland AFB, Albuquerque, New Mexico. 11:02 p.m. (MST). USAF 1st Lt. George E. Funk Jr., [Radar] Duty Controller, 135th AC&W Sq, Kirtland AFB, saw an almost stationary yellow-orange light at 240° azimuth (about WSW) at about 3,000 ft altitude, seen through a surveyor's transit [theodolite] for 3 mins, [naked eye 7 mins], along with Airman/1C K. D. Peebles, Airman/1C W. M. Stamps [sp?], and Airman 2/C C. D. Bolts Jr. Object faded, no radar contact. (Sparks 750; BB files; Berliner)

**Military Reports During November 3 to 7, 1957 Involving Multiple Incidents During a Day.
From the Sparks catalog**

November. 3, 1957. 9 miles E of Levelland, 1 mile W of Smyer, Texas. 12:05 a.m. Texas Tech college student Newell H. Wright was driving W when the ammeter on his car dashboard started fluctuating widely, car motor gradually went out then headlights and radio died. He got out to check and saw a white or aluminum-colored oval-shaped object flat on the bottom like a loaf of bread, with a greenish tint, about 75-125 ft long. After a few mins object suddenly rise up from the road ahead and ascend almost vertically at great speed, slightly to the N, disappearing in secs. Afterward car was able to be restarted. (Sparks 1261; Hynek UFO Exp ch. 9; Tony Rullán; Vallée Magonia 419)

November 3, 1957. White Sands Proving Ground (WSPG), New Mexico. 2:30-3 a.m. (MST). Army Cpl. Glenn H. Toy and PFC James E. Wilbanks, Army Garrison Detachment 5, WSPG, in a jeep patrol driving N, located S of Stallion Site, saw an orange or fire-like, "apparently controlled," egg-shaped luminous object about 120 ft (PFC estimate) 225-300 ft (Cpl. estimate) in size, first high in the sky descending to 60-80 ft (PFC estimate) or 150 ft (Cpl. estimate) above ground, hovering for 3 mins (then disappeared for a few mins and reappeared almost as bright as the sun, then fell at about a 40° angle to the ground as if landing and light went out, about 2-3 miles away at the N end of the test grounds. Possibly the nearly Full Moon which set about 3:30 a.m. (MST) in the W. (Sparks 1262; BB files; Magonia 420; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

November 3, 1957. White Sands Proving Ground, New Mexico. 8 p.m. (MST). Army Spec-3 Henry R. Barlow and Spec-3 Forest R. Oakes, Army Garrison Detachment 5, WSPG, in a jeep patrol driving W near the site of the first A-bomb explosion, Trinity Site, saw a pulsating red then white light, possibly 200-300 ft in size about 4-5 miles away, brightening and dimming sometimes going out, rising in the sky from the ground (per Spec-3 A) or from about 50 ft over the bunker (per Spec-3 Z) up to about 45° elevation until it looked like a star or point source then disappeared. Possibly Venus in the SW setting at about 8:30 p.m. (MST). (Sparks 1263; BB files; Magonia 420; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

November 4, 1957. About 8-10 [4?] miles SSW of Orogrande, New Mexico (at about 32° 18' N, 106° 8' W, elev. 4100 ft). 1:10 p.m. (MST). James Stokes, electronics instrumentation technician, Rocketsonde Branch, High Altitude Test Division, AF Missile Development Center, Holloman AFB, NM, a Mr. Duncan of Las Cruces, NM, and Allan Baker of Holloman AFB. Stokes was driving S down Hwy 54 when his radio faded and the car slowed [stopped?] as if the battery was failing then he noticed 6-12 cars ahead of him had stopped and drivers were out looking at the sky (looking behind him to the NE), including Duncan and Baker. Stokes stopped and got out, saw pearl-white oval or egg-shaped object about 500 ft wide with slight purplish tinge heading S at high speed estimated 1500-2000 mph from the NE below elevation angle of Sacramento Mtns ridgeline (about 1°), descending from about 5,000 ft above ground level in shallow dive to about 1,500-2,500 ft AGL as it swerved to the W to pass to the S of Stokes and the other stopped cars about 2 or 3-5 miles at closest, then circling around headed W and disappearing. The same or another object appeared in the NE (as if the object had completely circled) and performed same rounded course but passing farther to the S of the parked cars [about 5 miles?] and disappeared in the W. Duncan took 35 mm film of the object. Stokes noticed a wave of heat from the object at closest approach, later that evening was sunburned, but it cleared up the next day. (Sparks 1264; APRO; BB files; McDonald list; Saunders/FUFOR Index; etc.)

November 4, 1957. Elmwood Park, Illinois (at 41°56.3' N,

87°49' W). 3:12-3:22 [3?] [3:15?] a.m. (CST). Police officers Joseph Lukasek and Clifford Schau and fireman Daniel De Giovanni on patrol noticed unexplained dimming of their spotlight and headlights, saw setting-sunlike orange globe straight ahead down the street to the W [street oriented to 268° azimuth], various maneuvers as they pursued it over 1-1/2 miles and U-turns, seen to N, passing over their car behind them to E and again W, approaching to within 150-300 ft [?]. Noiseless, changed to cigar shape at one point. Disappeared high up in the sky like a black shade pulled up from the bottom. Moon reportedly seen to the E [East of the UFO?] in clear sky. Moon at ~274° was to the right, or E of UFO at 268° (Moon at about 274°-275° setting at 276° at about 3:30 a.m., 90% full). Street oriented to 268° so Moon not visible through ½ mile of buildings lining alleyway of W. Wellington Ave. Independent witness Helmut Reuter saw the red-orange cigar-shaped object to the W at 3:15 a.m. from 73rd Ave., Elmwood Park. (Sparks 1265; Hynek UFO Rpt pp. 172-6; Vallée Magonia 421; Loren Gross Nov. 3- 5, 1957, pp. 22-27; Herb Taylor)

November 4, 1957. 3 miles SE of El Paso Airport, Texas. 7:30 p.m. Border Patrol inspector Burton saw egg-shaped object with bluish glow approaching from the SW at 30° elevation with whirring sound like artillery shell after car stalled and headlights dimmed and blacked out. Object passed over car at 100 ft height headed W, changing altitude at irregular intervals, rose vertically at Franklin Mtns. (Sparks 1266; Hynek UFO Rpt p. 181; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

November 4, 1957. Kirtland AFB (at 35° 3' N, 106°38' W) and Manzano Base/Site A National Nuclear Stockpile, Albuquerque, New Mexico. 10:45 p.m. (MST). CAA air traffic controllers R. M. Kaser and E. G. Brink saw a highly maneuverable 15-20 ft egg-shaped object with a white light at its base circle over the W [E?] end of the base at 150-200 mph and come down in a steep 30° dive as if landing on Runway 26, to the N or NW of the tower at about 1500 ft. Radar tracked part of this maneuver. Object then crossed flight line, runways and taxiways heading towards the tower at about 50 mph and 20-30 ft above ground, observed through 7x binoculars till it reached about 3,000 ft to the ENE near the NE corner of the floodlit restricted nuclear Weapons Storage Area / Area D/Drumhead Area (Manzano Base/Site A National Nuclear Stockpile), and a B-58 bomber service site, where it hovered for 20 secs-1 min then headed E again, at about 200-300 ft height, then suddenly shot up at a steep climb at about 45,000 [4,500?] ft/min. Controllers contacted RAPCON which tracked object on CPN-18 radar traveling E then turning S, circling the Albuquerque Low Frequency Range Station then headed N [disappearing at 10 miles and reappearing 20 mins later to circle around ?] to follow 1/2 mile behind a USAF C-46 that had just taken off to the S for 14 miles until both went off scope. Hovering radar target then appeared to the N over outer marker for 1-1/2 mins before fading. (Sparks 1267; McDonald 1968, 1972; Hynek UFO Exp ch. 7, case RV-3)

November 5, 1957. Long Beach Airport, Calif. Zibello. (Sparks 1268; McDonald list; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

November 5, 1957. Eglin AFB, Florida. (Sparks 1269; McDonald list)

November 5, 1957. About 200 [350?] miles S of Mobile (at 25° [27°?] 47' N, 89°24' W) and near Selma, Alabama. 5:16- 5:23? a.m. US Coast Guard cutter Sebago heading NNE at 23° azimuth tracked radar target to the S at 188° azimuth range 22 miles traveling at 650 mph disappearing at 190° azimuth at 55 miles range. Visual object like a brilliant planet was seen at 5:21 for 5 secs traveling left to right from W to NW from 270° to 310° azimuth at about 31° elevation. A radar target seemingly stationary for 1 min at 5:20-21 to the N at 350° azimuth range 7 miles moved slowly towards the NE then accelerated rapidly off the scope at 15° azimuth (about NNE) at 175 miles. 3 USAF pilots at Selma saw

a bright object flash from S to N, time uncertain. (Sparks 1270; Hynek-CUFOS-Willy Smith files; cf. CR p. 165)

November 5, 1957. Scotia, Nebraska (41.46° N, 98.68° W). 5:30 p.m. Winslow heard helicopter-like noise, smelled "burning" odor, saw a balloon-like, elongated object coming to ground level, without touching down, emanating thick smoke, then object rose again and disappeared. Witness was "paralyzed" during sighting. (Sparks 1271; Vallée Magonia 424; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

Nov. 6, 1957. Kagoshima, Japan (31°37' N, 130°32' E). (Sparks 1272; McDonald list)

Nov. 6, 1957. Laredo AFB, Texas. (Sparks 1273; McDonald list)

Nov. 6, 1957. Whiteman AFB, Missouri. (Sparks 1274; McDonald list)

Nov. 6, 1957. N of Seoul, South Korea (at 37°30' N, 127° E ?). Morning. A luminous bluish-white barrel-shaped object was seen close to the ground, reflected in a pool of water. It rose and vanished "like a light switched off." (Sparks 1275; Vallée Magonia 426)

Nov. 6, 1957. Santa Fe, New Mexico. 12:10 a.m. J. Martinez and A. Gallegos saw an egg-shaped object slowly coming toward them at low altitude, illuminating their car, producing a humming sound. Car engine, clock and a wristwatch stopped. Object shot away to the SW. (Sparks 1276; Vallée Magonia 425; BB files??)

Nov. 6, 1957. Boerne, Texas. 6 p.m. McGregor saw an oval object, about 15 ft long, bright orange similar to glowing coals, hovering 12 ft above ground. He went to call his family, but the object had vanished when he returned. Tape [?]. (Sparks 1277; cf. Vallée Magonia 431; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

Nov. 6, 1957. Lake County, Ohio. 6:30 a.m. Markell saw an unbearably bright round object, much larger than a plane, landing on a ridge, then taking off again. Object had an "odd color," left no trail, made no noise. (Sparks 1278; Vallée Magonia 428; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

Nov. 6, 1957. Montville, Ohio (41.62° N, 81.06° W). 11:30 [11:20] p.m. (EST). Olden J. Moore, 28, a plasterer, while driving home suddenly saw an object like a bright meteor split into two pieces, one going straight up, the other getting larger while color changing from bright white to blue-green. Object hovered 200 ft above a field close to ground, 500 ft away, with a soft whirring sound. After 15 mins, Moore walked to the object, which was shaped like "a covered dish" 50 ft in diameter, 15 ft high, with a cone on top about 10 ft high, surrounded by haze or fog, pulsating slowly. Holes, footprints and decaying radioactivity found at the site by Civil Defense Director Kenneth Locke about 12 (?) hours later, a maximum of 150 microR/hr at the center of a 100-foot UFO hovering/landing site area, decaying to 20 microR/hr 3 hours later, suggestive of an approximately 1-hour radionuclide half-life or less (e.g., if background level was 10 microR/hr then 140 decreased to 10 in 3 hours, or about ¾ hour half-life). Initial radioactivity level might have been $212 \approx 4,000x$ greater, for a 1 hr half-life, or about 0.6 R/hr. (Sparks 1279; Vallée Magonia 433; Michel-Mebane 1958; BB files)

Nov. 6, 1957. Radium Springs, New Mexico. 10:50 p.m. Las Cruces policeman [Barela?] and a Dona Ana County Deputy Sheriff saw a round object changing from red to green to blue to white rising vertically from a mountain top. (Sparks 1280; Berliner; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

Nov. 7, 1957. Harlingen AFB, Texas (26.18° N, 97.69° W). (Sparks 1281; McDonald list; Saunders/FUFOR Index)

Nov. 7, 1957. Amarillo, Texas. 7:45 p.m. AEC security guards and a Texas highway patrolman at the Pantex plutonium nuclear weapons assembly plant sighted 3 flashing objects that hovered for 30 mins over the plant only 50 ft in the air. The highway patrolman said the guards were "all shook up" when he got there. One object reportedly landed offsite. The guards attempted to approach it, but every time they got near, the object would slip away. BB case? (Sparks 1282; David Rudiak; Amarillo Globe-Times, Nov. 8, 1957)

Military Reports During 18 October 1975 to 10 November 1975.

October 18, 1975, 12:30 am, 25 miles NW of Helena, Montana, Near Great Falls AFB / Malmstrom AFB. John Struble was driving his truck when he noticed a large object, fifty feet in diameter and twenty-five to thirty feet in the air. The object passed over his truck from the rear and then stopped and hovered about one hundred yards ahead of him. As the object did this it directed a very bright light at him, causing the truck's lights and engine to go out. The UFO stayed there for about five minutes before moving away. The object made a noise like a big jet and then rocketed straight up into the sky and moved away to the east at an incredible speed. When the UFO disappeared the truck's lights and engine came back on. Struble noticed that his non-electric watch had stopped for five minutes, the duration of the UFO's appearance. (Reference: Lawrence Fawcett and Barry J. Greenwood, *Clear Intent*, page 33)

Note: 25 miles NW of Helena is around Wilborn on State Highway 279 and would place John Struble approximately 25 miles south of the closest Malmstrom ICBM silo.

October 27, 1975, 7:45 pm, Loring AFB/Limestone AFB, Maine. Staff Sgt. Danny K. Lewis was patrolling the weapons dump when he saw an unidentified aircraft nearing the north perimeter of Loring at a low altitude of about 300 feet. Lewis noticed what appeared to be a red navigation light and a white strobe light on the aircraft. As Lewis watched, the craft entered the perimeter of Loring. Meanwhile, in the control tower of the air base, Staff Sgt. James P. Sampley of the 2192nd Communications Squadron was on duty at the radar screen. He got a radar return from an unknown aircraft ten to thirteen miles east-northeast of Loring. Sampley made numerous attempts by radio on all available communications bands, civilian and military, to contact the craft, but he got no response. The unidentified craft began to circle and came to within 300 yards of the restricted nuclear storage area at a low altitude of 150 feet. Back at the nuclear weapons dump, Lewis notified his Command Post of the of the 42 Bomb Wing that an unknown aircraft had penetrated the base perimeter and was within 300 yards of the nuclear weapons area. The base was immediately put on major alert status, a Security Option 3, and Security contacted the tower. (CLEAR INTENT, 16-26; Barry: Greenwood and Larry: Fawcett)

October 27, 1975, 8:45 pm, Loring AFB/Limestone AFB, Maine. Sgt. Grover K. Eggleston of the 2192nd Communications Squadron was on duty at the tower when the call from the Command Post came. He began observing the unknown aircraft. Six minutes later, while watching the radar screen, Eggleston noted that the unknown craft appeared to be circling approximately ten miles east-northeast of the base. This action lasted for forty minutes when, suddenly, it disappeared from the screen. Either the object had landed, or it had dropped below the radar coverage. The Wing Commander arrived at the weapons storage area seven minutes after the initial sighting was made. Immediately, other units of the 42nd Police began pouring into the area. Security vehicles with blue flashing lights were converging from all over the base. Through the Loring Command Post, the Wing Commander requested fighter coverage from the 21st NORAD Region at Hancock Field, New York, and the 22nd NORAD Region at North Bay, Ontario, Canada. However, fighter support was denied by both regions. The Wing Commander then increased local security posture and requested assistance from the Maine State Police in trying to identify the unknown craft, which they presumed was a helicopter. A call was made to local flight services for possible identification, without results. The 42nd Security Police conducted a sweep of the weapons storage perimeter inside and out. An additional sweep was made of the areas that the craft had flown over. All actions produced no results. The craft broke the circling pattern and began flying toward Grand Falls, New Brunswick, Canada. Radar contact was lost in the vicinity of Grand

Falls bearing 065 degrees, twelve miles from Loring. Canadian authorities were not notified. No further unusual events occurred throughout that night. Priority messages were sent to the National Military Command Center in Washington, D.C., the Chief of Staff of the U.S. Air Force, the USAF Forward Operations Division at Fort Ritchie, Maryland, and Strategic Air Command headquarters at the 8th Air Force and the 45th Division informing them of what had taken place. The base remained on a high state of alert for the rest of the night and into the early morning hours of October 28. (CLEAR INTENT, 16-26; Barry: Greenwood and Larry: Fawcett)

October 28, 1975, 7:45-8:20 pm, Loring AFB/Limestone AFB, Maine. While patrolling the weapons storage area, Staff Sgt. Lewis, along with Sgt. Clifton W. Blakeslee and Sgt. Willi a.m. J. Long, again spotted the lights of an unidentified aircraft approaching Loring AFB from the north at an altitude of about 3,000 feet. It approached to within about three miles of the base perimeter and was noted to have a flashing white light and an amber or orange light. Lewis reported the sighting to his Command Post, and the Wing Commander came out to the weapons storage area to see for himself. He reported seeing an object with a flashing white light and an amber light whose speed and motion were similar to that of a helicopter. The craft was also observed on radar. The craft was then observed over the flight line by Sgt. Steven Eichner, Sgt. R. Jones, and others. They saw an orange and red object shaped like a stretched-out football hovering in mid-air. It turned out its lights, and then reappeared making jerky motions, then hovering about 150 feet over the end of the runway. It was described as about four car-lengths long, solid, reddish orange, with no doors or windows, and with no visible propellers or engines. It was totally silent. The base went on full alert and a sweep was made by security, but the object turned off its lights and was not seen again. Radar picked up a target moving in the direction of Grand Falls, New Brunswick. SAC Headquarters was again notified. NICAP

October 29, 1975, 1:00 a.m. EST, Loring AFB/Limestone AFB, Maine. Actual transcript: One unidentified helicopter was sighted 300 to 500 meters from the weapons storage area at Loring AFB, Maine. The helicopter was at an altitude of 150 feet and penetrated Loring AFB. An attempt to contact and identify the intruding "helicopter" was made by an Army National Guard helo and was unsuccessful. At 290300 EST the helicopter was sighted over the weapons storage area and the Army National Guard helicopter again responded to make contact but was unsuccessful. The USAF (Ops Div) has requested that the Army NG helo be provided until 300800 EST under the following conditions: To track and identify the intruder; no apprehension to take place; the Canadian Border would not be crossed; and civilian police on board will be for commo with ground units only. The request is under consideration by MG Snifin, DA Director of Operations, DCSOPS. Col Bailey, Mil Aide to Special Asst to SECDEF/DEPSECDEF has been advised of the situation show DoD approval be required. The State Department Canadian Desk Officer has been kept informed. (SOURCE: 42 BW CP LORING AFB 2911402 OCT 75; SAC CP OPS CONTROL 2919542 OCT 75. (NICAP)

October 29 (or 30), 1975, 4:00 p.m. (?) Wurtsmith AFB, Michigan. RAPCON crew contacted by tower and SAC about intrusion north of the base over restricted area. KC-135 made radar passes. One team member walked outside and saw disc hovering in daylight.

October 30, 1975, Loring AFB/Limestone AFB, Maine. The Maine National Guard Huey was replaced by an Air Force helicopter and crew from Plattsburgh AFB. That evening, objects were reported at several locations over and near the base and were detected by radar. (NICAP)

October 30, 1975; 10:10 pm, Wurtsmith AFB, Michigan. Personnel in the vicinity of the family housing area located in the southeastern portion of Wurtsmith reported seeing what appeared to be running lights of a low-flying craft which was thought to be a helicopter. The craft hovered and moved

up and down in an erratic manner. Airman Martin E. Tackabury, assigned to the Capehart housing area gate, said that he saw the object for about five seconds near the perimeter of Wurtsmith, due south of his location. Tackabury reported that the object had one white light pointing directly downward and two red lights near the rear. The object seemed to be heading in a west-southwest direction. Tackabury could not hear any sound coming from the aerial craft because a B-52 was in the air nearby to the north. Near the main gate at Wurtsmith, Airman Michael J. Myers, assigned to Police Unit Seven, was on duty at the Wurtsmith motor pool. As Myers looked toward the west, he could see several lights near the western edge of the base. The lights turned north and appeared to lose altitude. He did not hear any sound. Sergeant Robert J. Anderson, also at the motor pool, reported that he observed an airborne KC-135 tanker and another craft with a steady red light. The craft appeared to be flying slower, ahead and below the KC-135. Anderson believed he heard a sound similar to a helicopter. After thirty to thirty-five seconds, the object passed out of view. Airman Roger Skipper, at the Wurtsmith main gate, said that when he responded to the activity at the motor pool, he heard sounds that diminished quickly. (Clear Intent)

October 30, 1975, 10:14, 10:20, & 10:25 pm, Wurtsmith AFB, Michigan. At the back gate of Wurtsmith, security police reported to the command post that an unidentified helicopter with no lights came up over the back gate and hovered over the weapons storage area at a low altitude. Security police of the 379th security police squadron in the weapons storage area could not make out the type of craft. The craft started to move towards the northern perimeter where its lights were again turned on. Sergeant James A. Miller of the Wurtsmith security police reported his observations of the unknown craft while on duty in the weapons storage area. He stated that he heard the sound of a possible helicopter coming from an area off the base toward the north. He thought he had heard the sound of a flying helicopter fifteen minutes earlier, but he didn't report it. As he listened, the noise became drowned out by a military jet, and when the jet passed out of range, the original noise had stopped. No other similar sounds were heard. Security police at the weapon storage area notified Colonel John J. Doran, Vice Commander, 379th Bomb Wing, that the guard posted at the back gate had reported what he thought was a helicopter overhead. The command post notified Col. Boardman (wing commander) and Col. Doran, and they proceeded to the flight line. It was at this time that Radar Approach Control (RAPCON) reported low-flying objects on their radar scope. They tracked the craft for approximately thirty-five miles on a southeastern bearing from Wurtsmith.

October 30, 1975, 10:30 - 11:00 pm, Wurtsmith, Michigan. A KC-135 tanker was returning from a refueling mission. It entered Wurtsmith's traffic pattern and received permission to fly transition approaches. Col. Boardman ordered the KC-135 to attempt to identify the object. Wurtsmith air traffic control vectored the tanker in the object's direction. Aboard the KC-135 was Major Frederick Pappas, the plane's commander; Captain K. E. May, co-pilot; Captain Rick Meier, the navigator; Captain Myron Taylor, instructor navigator; Captain Randy Higginbotham, instructor pilot; and Sergeant Steve Smith. Captain Taylor: "We were returning from a refueling mission and during our first approach into the traffic pattern, RAPCON vectored us to check out a reported UFO in the area of the Wurtsmith Weapons Storage Area. As I recall, this activity occurred between 10:30 and 11:00 in the evening around the 1st of November (later established as Oct. 30). I remember seeing lights similar to strobe lights which were flashing irregularly. We followed the lights north out over Lake Huron and then the UFO swung south still over the lake toward the Saginaw Bay area of Michigan. At first it was difficult to determine whether there were two different objects because of the irregular flashing of the lights. But, after observing the lights we determined that there were in fact two objects and the irregular flashing appeared to be some sort of signal being passed from one to the other in an effort to maintain the same position. We were able to maintain visual contact most of the time and I was only able to paint an object on the radar scope for about 10 seconds. I would estimate that our altitude was about

2,000 feet and our speed approximately 200 knots. Shortly after turning south in pursuit of the UFO, we called Approach Control and received blanket clearance to follow the UFO at all altitudes and at all vectors. Occasionally, RAPCON would pick-up the UFO and help us by giving us vectors to the UFO's position. I would guess that we stayed close to the UFO most of the time, approximately one mile away, and each time we attempted to close on the object it would speed away from us. We followed the UFO down to Saginaw Bay and started across the Bay when we lost it because of all the fishing boat lights. At first, we thought it had landed on one of the large oil tankers but later decided that we had been wrong. We continued to search the Bay area but didn't see it, so we changed our heading for Wurtsmith. On the way back, we picked the UFO up again at our eight o'clock position. We turned away, and it proceeded to follow us. Finally, we turned back in the direction of the UFO, and it really took off back in the direction of the Bay area. I know this might sound crazy, but I would estimate that the UFO sped away from us doing approximately 1,000 knots. We continued in the direction of the Bay until RAPCON called us again and said they were painting a UFO four to five miles over the coast traveling in a westerly direction. They vectored us to the position of the UFO and we proceeded but at that point we were low on fuel and were forced to return to Wurtsmith. I remember that while on final approach we saw the lights again near the Weapons Storage Area. Following the mission, we discussed the incident and about a week later, Captain Higginbotham was questioned by the OSI and cautioned not to discuss the incident." (NICAP)

October 31, 1975, 11:17 p.m. EST, Loring AFB, Maine. A visual sighting of an unidentified object was reported 4 nautical miles NW of Loring AFB, Me. The alert Helo was launched to identify the object but was unable to make contact. The alert Helo was launched again at 0146 hours EST,

November 7, 1975, 3:35 a.m. MST, Moore, near Malmstrom AFB, Montana "Received a call from the 341st Strategic Air Command Post (SAC CP) saying that the following missile locations reported seeing a large red to orange to yellow object: M-1, L-3, LIMA, and L-6. The general object location would be 10 miles south of Moore, Montana, and 20 miles east of Buffalo, Montana. Commander Deputy [sic] for Operations (DO) informed." (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 3:38 am, West of Great Falls, Montana. Whitish gray UFO with blue lights. (NIDS UFO 15). (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 4:05 am. MST, Lewiston missile site, Montana. From SAC CP: E-1 reported a bright white light (site is approximately 60 nautical miles north of Lewiston). NCOC notified. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 5:03 a.m. MST, Harlow, near Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAC advised that the LCF at Harlow, Montana, observed an object which emitted a light which illuminated the site driveway. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 6:19 a.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAC advised K-1 saw a very bright object to their east is now southeast of them and they are looking at it with 10 x 50 binoculars. Object seems to have lights (several) on it, but no distinct pattern. The orange/gold object overhead also has small lights on it. SAC also advises female civilian reports having seen an object bearing south from her position 6 miles west of Lewiston. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 6:27 am, Malmstrom AFB, Montana MST. L-1 reports that the object to their northeast seems to be issuing a black object from it, tubular in shape. In all this time, surveillance has not been able to detect any sort of track except for known traffic. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 6:55 a.m. Malmstrom AFB, MT Montana. (Nov. 7, 1355Z) K-1 and L-1 report that as the sun rises, so do the objects they have visual. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 7:29 am, MST; Malmstrom AFB, Montana. (Nov. 7, 1429Z) From SAC CP: As the sun rose, the UFOs disappeared. Commander and DO notified. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (CLEAR INTENT, 29). (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 11:35 p.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. A security camper team at K-4 reported UFO with white lights, one red light 50 yards behind white light. Personnel at K-1 seeing same object. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, 11:45 p.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. Height personnel picked up objects 10 - 13,000 feet, Track J330, EKLB 0648, 18 knots, 9,500 feet. Objects as many as seven, as few as two NC. (24th NORAD Region Senior Director's log), (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, Malmstrom AFB, Montana Time not given. Then, yet another sighting was reported. An off-duty missile launch officer, and his deputy had just retired for crew rest in the Soft Support Building (SSB). The deputy went to the window and observed the silhouette of a large aircraft hovering about ten to fifteen feet above the ground and about twenty-five feet outside the Launch Control Facility. He described two red and white lights at the front of the aircraft, a white light on the bottom, and white light on the rear. The craft hovered motionless in this position for about one minute and then departed. The missile launch officer did not personally observe the aircraft, but from its sound, he speculated that it was a helicopter. The deputy also felt that the sounds he heard were those of a helicopter. The deputy's observations were limited by the darkness of the night, which prevented any good description of the craft or its shape. (NICAP)

November 7, 1975, Lewiston, Montana. Remote electronic sensors triggered an alarm indicating that something was violating site security. Underground, in the launch control area, two officers noted the signal, but there was no television surveillance topside. The normal procedure for detecting what had violated security was to call for a missile security helicopter to check the area. At the same time, Sabotage Alert Teams (SAT), consisting of four to six men, were also alerted to the fact that a violation was taking place and were ordered to proceed to the site. On this occasion, an SAT team drove down the highway and onto a dirt road which led to the K-7 area. About a mile away, the team could see an orange, glowing object over the area. As they closed to within half a mile, they could now see that the object was tremendous in size. They radioed to the Launch Control Facility that, from their location, they were viewing a brightly glowing, orange, football field-sized disc that illuminated the missile site. The SAT team was ordered by the launch control people to proceed into the K-7 site. However, they responded that they refused to go any farther, clearly fearful of the intimidating appearance of the object. It began to rise, and at about 1,000 feet, NORAD picked up the UFO on radar. Two F-106 jet interceptors were launched from Great Falls, Montana, and headed toward the K-7 area. The UFO continued to rise. At about 200,000 feet, it disappeared from NORAD's radar. The F-106's was never able to get a visual sighting of the UFO. All members of the SAT team were directed to the base hospital, where they were psychologically tested. It was determined that no one could identify the

object that was seen, but that the members of the SAT team obviously had been through a traumatic experience. Meanwhile, targeting teams, along with computer specialists, were brought to the missile site to check out the missile, and specifically, the computer in the warhead that targets the missile. Amazingly, when the computer was checked, they found that the tape had mysteriously changed target numbers! The re-entry vehicle was then taken from the silo and brought back to the base. Eventually the entire missile was changed. (Clear Intent, 27) **Note:** The source and documentation for the report above, including the actual times, is being sought. As Brad Sparks pointed out recently, the big problem here is that the NORAD radar couldn't track a target up to "200,000 feet." The Malmstrom AFB height finder FPS-90 radar in operation in 1975 couldn't height-find anything above the maximum 75,000 feet shown on the display. (NICAP)

November 8, 1975, 12:53 am, MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. Received seven radar cuts on the height finder radar at altitudes between 9,500 and 15,500 feet. Simultaneous ground witnesses observed lights in the sky and the sound of jet engines similar to jet fighters. Cross-tell with FAA revealed no jet aircraft within 100 NM of the sighting. Radar tracked the objects over Lewiston, Montana, at a speed of 7 knots. Two F-106 interceptors from the 24th NORAD Region were scrambled at 0254 EST, and became airborne at 0257 EST. At the time of the initial voice report, personnel at Malmstrom AFB and SAC sites K-1, K-3, L-3, and L-6 were reporting lights in the sky accompanied by jet engine noise. (CLEAR INTENT, 30; NMCC Docs751108.12dt). (NICAP)

November 8, 1975, 1:44 am. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. Objects could not be intercepted. Fighters had to maintain a minimum of 12,000 feet because of mountainous terrain. Sightings had turned west, increased speed to 150 knots. Two tracks were apparent on height-finder radars 10-12 NM apart. SAC site K-3 reported sightings between 300 feet and 1,000 feet, while site L-4 reported sightings 5 NM from the position. Sightings disappeared from radar at position 4650 N/10920 W at a tracked speed of three (3) knots. (CLEAR INTENT, 31; NMCC Docs751108.12dt). (NICAP)

November 8, 1975, 2:05 a.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAC Site L-5 observed one object accelerate and climb rapidly to a point in altitude where it became indistinguishable from the stars. NORAD will carry this incident as a FADE remaining UNKNOWN at 3:20 EST since after that time only visual sightings occurred." (Note: There is an Air Force term used to describe an incident in which a nuclear device is tampered with. This term is "Faded Giant," a phrase which very appropriately describes the K-7 report. [Clear Intent, 28; (NMCC Docs751108.12dt)]). (NICAP)

November 8, 1975, 2:05 a.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. Malmstrom receiving intermittent tracks on both search and height-finder radars. SAC site C-1, 10NM SE of Stanford, Montana, reported visual sightings of unknown objects.

November 8, 1975, 2:20 a.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. Personnel at 4 SAC sites reported observing intercepting F-106s arrive in area; sighted objects turned off their lights upon arrival of interceptors, and back on upon their departure.

November 8, 1975, 2:40 a.m. MST, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAC site C-1 still had a visual sighting on objects. At 6:00 a.m. EST, the National Military Command Center in Washington, D.C., distributed a "Memorandum for the Record." The subject was "Unidentified Sightings." This memo addressed the incidents above. (NMCC Docs751108.12dt) (NICAP)

November 8, 1975, 8:35 pm, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAT teams at sites K-3 and L-4 were reporting that they had visual sightings on the objects, with K-3 reporting targets at an altitude of 300 feet. As the F-106s arrived at the location, SAT teams reported that the UFOs turned their lights off. The F-106s, in searching for the unknowns, never gained a visual or radar contact at any time because of the low altitude of the UFOs. However, when they left the area, the UFOs would turn their lights back on! At 9:15 P.M., four different locations were reporting that they had the UFOs and fighters in sight. The UFOs seemed to be playing a cat-and mouse game.

November 8, 1975, 9:53 pm, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. The team at L-5 reported to the Command Post that the unknowns had increased in speed, climbed rapidly, and, at that point, could not be distinguished from the stars. A while later, the team at site E-1 reported at 11:05 pm. that a bright white light was seen approximately sixty nautical miles north of Lewiston.

November 9, 1975, 3:05 am, Malmstrom AFB, Montana. SAC crews at sites L-1, L-6, and M-1 observed a UFO. They described it as being a yellowish, bright, round light twenty miles north of Harlowton at an altitude of 2,000 to 4,000 feet. At 3:20 a.m., the SAC Command Post reported the UFO twenty miles southeast of Lewiston. The color of the object was reported as orange-white, and its appearance was round or disc-shaped. (CLEAR INTENT, 31) (NICAP)

November 10, 1975, Minot AFB, North Dakota. A long entry from the 24th NORAD Region Senior Director's Log said: "UFO sighting reported by Minot Air Force Station, a bright star-like object in the west, moving east, about the size of a car. First seen approximately 1015. Approximately 1120, the object passed over the radar station, 1000-2000 feet high, no noise heard.